

Role and Responsibilities of Indian Media about Child Abuse

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Abstract

The media has played a key role in the construction of child abuse as a major social problem. From a largely unacknowledged issue reportage of child abuse has now reached saturation point. Moreover, the issue has been covered across a range of genre (including news programmes, TV drama, films, call-in shows, soap operas) thereby reaching a diverse range of audiences. While acknowledging the importance of the media in raising awareness, some commentators have also noted that the media’s interest is very recent and has generally relied on others (e.g. activists, professional groups) to lay the groundwork. So this paper is discussed about the how the media play an important role in strategies to prevent child abuse

Introduction

Abuse and neglect are defined as “injury, sexual abuse, sexual exploitation, negligent treatment or maltreatment of a child”. This abuse can be of several kinds according to the World Health Organisation (WHO) – physical, mental, emotional, psychological or in the form of neglect or exploitation. It brings about circumstances causing harm to a child’s health, welfare, and safety. Child abuse, in its various forms can be found everywhere in India - in cities and rural homes, in the homes of the rich and the poor, and in the streets and schools. Wiping out child abuse in India requires a complex strategy that will require multi-stakeholder support.

Role of Indian Media in Child Abuse

Indian Media is an extremely important and powerful tool in achieving the civil society goals of ensuring child rights and exerting pressure to hold government accountable for them. The Indian media is repeatedly criticized for its lack of adequate, balanced coverage on child-related issues, and the absence of children’s voices in news reporting.

Indian media is not just accused of not doing enough for the child rights besides they are questioned regularly for insensitive representation of children in their news stories.

The Juvenile Justice (Care and Protection of Children) Act 2000 is clear that no child who conflicts with law should be named or his photograph published. In 2007, the National Commission for Protection of Child Rights had received complaints on the use of the name and photographs of an 8-year old boy in Begusarai, Bihar, who is alleged to have killed three children, was referred to in reports as a ‘serial killer’ and a ‘tyrant’. The TOI headlines of Jun 1, 2007, reads, “Eight-year-old ‘serial killer’ held after third murder”.

According to a report by child rights NGO CRY, sexual offense is committed against a child in India every 15 minutes and there has been an increase of more than 500 percent over the past ten years in crime against minors.

“While Uttar Pradesh tops the list with 15 percent of recorded crimes against children, Maharashtra and Madhya Pradesh closely follow with 14 percent and 13 percent respectively,” the report said.

Responsibilities of Media About Child Abuse in India

Upholding the principles of its role as the fourth pillar of democracy, the media has a responsibility to bring the issue of child sexual abuse into the realm of public debate. It is integral that the issue gets highlighted, is given due attention and recognized by masses as a gruesome offense against children.

Albeit the responsibility bestowed upon the media, it is saddening to see the sensationalisation that the media at large is engaging in instead of sensitive reporting, as is expected of it.

Some of the headlines from reports that have come out in the print media in the recent past.

1. Girl ‘raped’ by youth in Thane
2. 11-year-old rape victim gives birth to child
3. 6-year-old girl raped in crèche, owner’s husband booked
4. Eighteen-month-old child raped by her uncle in Uttar Pradesh
5. 4-year-old ‘raped’, left bleeding on street
6. Nine-year-old critical after rape, undergoes surgeries

The news stories go on to talk about the details of the incident and at times even divulge personal details of the child and the family, in complete violation of the principles of confidentiality under the POCSO Act, 2012 and the JJ Act.

While reporting sexual abuse, the media needs to keep in mind the best interest of the child, namely:

1. Highlight the perpetrator his/her demography, background, brutality of his/her act rather than the demographics of the victim
2. Bring blame and shame towards the perpetrator rather than highlight the stigmatization of the child who was abused.
3. When reporting on sexual violence against children also report on the steps taken by the authorities to address and prevent such incidents; as well as the responsibility of adult citizens in intervening and preventing abuse.
4. Simultaneously run programs that highlight the fact that ensuring the safety and dignity of children is the responsibility of adults, as well as help adults learn how to teach Personal Safety to small children without instilling fear or distrust of adults.
5. Follow up the case/s intermittently until the trial is completed.
6. Moral and sex education should be made compulsory in schools and colleges.
7. Pornographic literature and blue films should be banned.
8. Sexual predators should be treated using psychological or medical techniques.
9. Separate tribunals/courts should be constituted specifically for cases of sexual abuse. Penalties should be severe to discourage those who might be contemplating such an act.

10. Awareness of sexual abuse could be created through mass media.
11. School officials could learn about signs and symptoms of childhood sexual abuse identification purposes. Further, specific action in reporting such cases should be outlined.

Impact of Media on Children

The influence of the media on the psychosocial development of children is profound. Television has the potential to generate both positive and negative effects, and many studies have looked at the impact of television on society, particularly on children and adolescents.

Most researchers agree that aggressive children and adolescents are more prone to the negative effects of TV violence than those who are not aggressive. Moreover, the harm is much greater for children who are preadolescent, especially those younger than eight years of age, as they still face some amount of difficulty in separating fantasy from reality. However, many studies show that all children are susceptible to harm from exposure to TV violence.

Conclusion

Child protection involves both the accommodation of cultural diversity while assuring equitable standards of care and protection for all children. Neighbourhood-based strategies to reduce and prevent child maltreatment will be enhanced by understanding Also, the presence of social networks and supports in the lives of children and families is a crucial factor in child well-being and the prevention of all forms of child abuse

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